

NOTES ON CONTRIBUTORS

Marina Tunițchi: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, Ukrainian Language and Literature Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți; 3) author of 70 scientific and didactic works; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) research areas: applied linguistics.

Angela Coșciug: 1) Ph.D.; 2) Associate Professor, French Philology Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți; 3) member of the Scientific Specialization Seminar for the Defense of the Doctoral Theses, speciality 10.02.05 – Romance languages (Moldova State University); 4) member of the Scientific Specialization Council for the Defense of the Doctoral Theses, speciality 10.02.05 – Romance languages (Moldova State University); 5) scientific adviser (since 2010) and reviewer of doctoral theses in Romance philology, national expert of textbooks of French for pre-university establishments from the Republic of Moldova; 6) since 2007, post-doctoral studies, Moldova State University; 7) author of 80 scientific and didactic works (monographs, essays, studies, textbooks, guides, courses of lectures, articles, abstracts) published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes (in Moldova, Romania, Russia, Canada, Albania etc.); 8) organizer of scientific conferences in Republic of Moldova and abroad; 9) publisher of scientific national and international conference volumes; 10) participant in 85 national and international scientific conferences; 11) editor-in-chief of *Speech and Context* International Journal of Linguistics, Semiotics and Literary Science; editor-in-chief of *Glotodidactica* Biannual Journal of Applied Linguistics; 12) member of the Scientific Board of *Мова ме Іcmопуя/Language and History* Journal published at Taras Șevcenko National University of Kiev, Ukraine, of the Scientific Board of *Communication Interculturelle et Littérature/Intercultural Communication and Literature* Journal published at Dunărea de Jos University of Galați, Romania, of the Scientific Board of *Concordia Discors vs Discordia Concors* Journal published at Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava, Romania, of the Scientific Board of *Interstudia* Journal published at the University of Bacau, Romania, of the Scientific Board of *Universalia* Journal published at Gheorghe Dima University of Arts and Design, Bucarest, Romania, of the Scientific Board of *African Political Science and International Relations*, Nigeria; 13) Grant of the French Government (2007); 14) member of Russian Association of Communication and Romanian Association of Bible Philological and Hermeneutical Studies; 15) research areas: Romance linguistics, general semiotics, literary semiotics, discourse theory, specialized French Language, translation studies, Francophone literature, Applied Linguistics, Contrastive linguistics.

Natalia Botezat: 1) Lecturer, Alecu Russo State University of Balti, Republic of Moldova; PhD, Moldova State University; 2) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 3) author of scientific and didactic works.

Irina Sitailo: 1) teacher of English, *N. Gogol* Lyceum, Bălți, Republic of Moldova; 2) participant in national seminars on applied linguistics; 3) author of didactic works.

Stella Gorbani: 1) Senior Lecturer, Alecu Russo State University of Balti, Republic of Moldova; 2) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 3) author of scientific and didactic works.

Roxolana Galit: 1) MA, Alecu Russo State University of Balti, Republic of Moldova; 2) participant in national seminars on applied linguistics; 3) author of didactic works.

Ecaterina Niculcea: 1) Lecturer, German Philology Department, Alecu Russo State University of Bălți; 2) secretary of *Glotodidactica* Journal of Applied Linguistics; 3) author of 12 scientific works published in prestigious national and international journals and volumes; 4) participant in national and international scientific conferences; 5) winner of several grants offered by universities from Germany and Switzerland; 6) research areas: German literature, comparative literature.